

A Systematic Evaluation of the Implementation a Speed Limit Data Exchange Mechanism Between Public Works Department of Cyprus and Map-Makers

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Abstract

This paper provides a systematic analysis of the implementation of a speed limit data exchange mechanism between the Public Works Department of Cyprus (PWD) and map-makers which was developed under the project TN-ITS GO using the CEN/TC 17268:2018 standard. Utilizing a robust data chain analysis method, we thoroughly map the data flow and identify key stakeholders, enabling a systematic evaluation of the data chain. Our study uncovers gaps in the Cypriot implementation of the mechanism and proposes effective mitigation measures. We found that while the TN-ITS data chain is effective, it presents unique challenges due to its multi-stakeholder nature, necessitating the active engagement of all parties involved. By addressing identified challenges and gaps, the data chain can be optimized for improved performance. The insights gathered from this study can be used to enhance other TN-ITS data chain services.

Keywords:

TN-ITS, Data Quality, Data Chain, Data Exchange

Introduction

Digitisation has become vital for the growth of any industry [1]. The automotive industry is rushing to develop fully autonomous vehicles to meet the demands for the future of mobility [2–4]. Along with the in-vehicle technological advancement in sensors and sensing, the use of high-quality, accurate and up-to-date maps for route planning, route optimisation and scheduling are a necessity [5,6]. Drivers and cars access information regarding the road network infrastructure using optical sensors reading traffic signs and through navigators usually provided by map makers [1,7–9]. However, map-makers update their maps once every few months or years by making field surveys which are time-consuming and costly [7]. Yet, the road network is constantly changing by road authorities following regulation changes making any survey valid only for a short period of time. Focusing on regulations related to speed limits, the EU legislation made Intelligent Speed Assistance (ISA) mandatory for all new vehicles starting in 2022, and mandatory for all existing carlines per 2024 [2,10–12]. ISA, also known as intelligent speed adaptation, is a system that ensures that vehicle speed does not exceed a safe or legally enforced speed. ISA uses a sign-recognition camera and/or GPS-linked speed limit data to inform drivers of the current speed limit and limit the speed of the vehicle as needed. GPS-linked speed limit data are usually retrieved from maps provided by navigators, and they are compared with the camera readings for validation. Consequently, moving to a more automated future, it is important to have accurate and up-to-date data within

the navigators.

Road authorities and map-makers in efforts to harmonize, enhance and speed up the exchange of data related to changes on static road attributes such as speed limits, through the projects the ROSATTE [13] and TN-ITS GO [7] they contributed in the creation of the TN-ITS Specification which defines the exchange format (structure and encoding) for the exchange [14]. This developed standard was later become a CEN Standard with the name” CEN/TC 278. CEN/TS 17268:2018 Intelligent Transport Systems—Its Spatial Data—Data Exchange on Changes in Road Attributes”. Furthermore, the TN-TIS (CEN/TS17268) it is mentioned on the Delegated Regulation 2022/670 with regards to the provision of EU-wide real-time traffic information services as one of the preferred standards for accessibility, exchange and re-use of data on infrastructure (Article 4) and on regulations and restrictions (Article 5) [8]. However, keeping a speed limit database up-to-date it can be complicated since several stakeholders might be involved in this process.

Objective

The objective of this paper is to identify potential gaps in the data chain of implementations purposed to produce data in the TN-ITS standard by using a real use case of changing a speed limit in Cyprus. The developed methodology can be used by other countries to evaluate their TN-ITS service.

Background

In line with the EU ITS Directive 2010/40/EU [15], now amended by 2023/2661 [12] and Delegated Regulations 886/2013 [16], 2022/670 [8], and 2017/1926 [8], the Public Works Department (PWD) of Cyprus with cooperation of the KIOS Research and Innovation Center of Excellence at the University of Cyprus have collaboratively developed a comprehensive Geographical Information System (GIS) for Intelligent Transport, known as the “GNOSIS” platform [17]. This platform, aims to facilitate the implementation of Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) across Cyprus and serves as the primary GIS system for managing the Cypriot primary road network, including its ITS equipment, road furniture and regulations. The backbone of the “GNOSIS” platform is a spatial database, which includes several elements of the road network, including a database dedicated to speed limits.

Cyprus implemented the TN-ITS service under the TN-ITS GO project [6] and it was launched in 2019 (<https://www.traffic4cyprus.org.cy/>). The scope of the TN-ITS GO project was to enhance already existed mechanism for the exchange of rod-related spatial data as well as to support member states to develop pilot services to enable exchange of rod-related spatial data. The PWD, acting as a beneficiary in this project developed a pilot service focused on the road network they manage, which includes Motorways/‘A’ Roads, Urban Roads and roads constructed after a wide urban planning are managed [7]. The primary function of the TN-ITS service is to monitor changes in speed limits in the GNOSIS speed limit database. Once a change is recorded, an XML file, conforming to the CEN/TS 17268:2018 standard, is published through the National Access Point. During the TN-ITS GO project the Cyprus TN-ITS service was positively evaluated under the

CEN/TS 17268:2018. Specifically, the evaluation was based on the performance of the web-service, the structure of the data based on the standard and on the content.

Identifying the Cyprus TN-ITS data chain for changing a speed limit

Despite the positive evaluation of the service during the TN-ITS GO project, PWD aims to expand the geographic coverage of the TN-ITS Cyprus Service while at the same time improving the quality of the data in terms of accuracy and timeliness with priority on the speed limits to comply with the Delegated Regulation 2022/670. To enhance the data accuracy and timeliness, it is important to evaluate the whole data chain of the TN-ITS.

In order to identify the TN-ITS data chain it was important to identify the main stakeholders in the process of changing a speed limit which are the following:

- **Police:** Responsible speed enforcement to prevent drivers exceeding the speed limit.
- **Police Chief:** Responsible to approve any requests for changes in speed limits under “The Motor Vehicles and Traffic Law of 1972 (86/1972)”
- **Police Office for Road Safety:** Responsible to inform authorities for the changes in speed limits.
- **Public Works Department:** Responsible for the maintenance and management of the Motorways/‘A’ Roads, Urban Roads and roads constructed after a wide urban planning are managed. Also, responsible to change the physical traffic sign of speed limit if instructed by the Police Office for Road Safety.
- **Local Authorities:** Responsible for the maintenance and management of the rest of the road network which mainly includes ‘B’ roads and local roads. Also, responsible to change the physical traffic sign of speed limit if instructed by the Police Office for Road Safety.
- **Citizens:** Responsible to maintain their vehicle speed under the dedicated maximum or over the minimum speed limit.

Speed limit Change data flow

Stakeholder identification interviews were performed with representatives from the Police and PWD to identify and map the data flow for changing a speed limit. Local Authorities were not interviewed since the scope of this study is related to the primary road network managed by PWD. Using the collected data, the following flow was recorded:

1. Any citizen or authority may submit a request to the Police Chief for a change in the speed limit in a specific area, accompanied by the reason for the requested change.
2. The Police Chief may approve or reject the request. If needed, a site visit will be instructed to the Office of Road Safety to collect more data.
3. If the request is approved, the approval is forwarded to the Police Office of Road Safety, which will prepare a letter with instructions to change the speed limit. This letter is sent to the authority responsible for the part of the road network where the speed limit change is proposed.
4. The authorities, which can be either the PWD or a local authority, need to take the necessary actions to

change the speed limit according to the instructions of the Police Chief.

The above flow is also shown in the below flow diagram (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - Speed limit change data flow

Identifying the Cyprus TN-ITS data chain for recording a speed limit digitally

Road authorities in Cyprus, including local authorities and the PWD, are responsible for the installation and maintenance of road signs, including speed limits. Currently, there is no legal framework or obligation for road authorities to maintain a digital record of speed limit locations or any changes to them. A few local authorities have a GI-based system and thus spatial information related to the road network, capable of including such a database. This paper focuses on the primary road network managed by PWD. As mentioned, the PWD has the “GNOSIS” GIS-based platform, which includes a database schema for traffic signs. To populate this database, the PWD used two methodologies: performing large-scale surveys in one region of the island, and using crowdsourced data via the Mapillary API [18]. With these methodologies, the PWD claims to have collected speed limit data for 95% of the road network they manage. Furthermore, the “GNOSIS” platform has a specialized tool for adding, deleting, or editing a specific speed limit. This tool was designed to add new speed limits and update existing ones based on instructions from the Police Office of Road Safety.

The TN-ITS Cyprus service reads the PWD Speed limit database and if any change occurs then automatically an XML file is produced using the TN-ITS standard and it is published on the Cyprus National Access Point

(Figure 2).

Figure 2 - PWD speed limit change data flow and TN-ITS export

Evaluation of the TN-ITS Data chain

To evaluate the TN-ITS service, a systematic approach was adopted in collaboration with the. The evaluation process comprised the following steps:

1. Retrieval of data from all changes recorded on the TN-ITS service.
2. Collection of data from all requests for speed limit changes.
3. Comparison of the requests with the recorded data on the TN-ITS service.
4. Analysis of the time intervals between all steps of the data flow to identify any potential delays.
5. Comparison of a sample of changes recorded on the TN-ITS service with the physical traffic signs to assess the integrity of the data.

The evaluation process started with the retrieval of all changes recorded on the TN-ITS Service. The service, launched in May 2019 and had recorded changes on only two days. A closer examination of these data, which were badge uploads related to a large-scale survey and data retrieved from the Mapillary API, prompted a discussion with the PWD. This led to an investigation of the entire data chain.

During the investigation, a communication gap was identified between the Police Office of Road Safety and the PWD personnel tasked with updating the traffic database on “GNOSIS” platform. Instructions for changing the traffic signs were directed solely to the department responsible for maintaining road equipment (as indicated by the red arrow in Figure 2). Consequently, neither the Police nor the department responsible for maintaining the road equipment was informing the department tasked with keeping the GIS database up-to-date. Given that the identified issue was related to organizational communication, it was not feasible to proceed with the subsequent steps of the evaluation.

Results and Next Steps

The evaluation of the TN-ITS service was conducted using a systematic approach in collaboration with the PWD. The process involved several steps, including data retrieval, comparison, and analysis. The results of the study revealed a significant communication gap in the data chain for changing speed limits, specifically between the Police Office of Road Safety and the PWD personnel responsible for updating the “GNOSIS” traffic database. This gap led to inability to record data on the TN-ITS service. The conclusion underscores the importance of effective communication and data flow in maintaining any information system. It also highlights the need for continuous evaluation and improvement of such systems to ensure the safety and efficiency of road transport in the era of digitisation and autonomous vehicles.

In order to improve the TN-ITS Service the following steps have been identified:

1. **Enhanced Communication:** Improve communication between stakeholders.
2. **Training:** Provide regular training to all stakeholders involved.
3. **Data Verification:** Implement a system for verifying the data entered into the system. This could involve cross-checking with other sources or using AI-based tools to detect anomalies.
4. **Feedback Mechanism:** Establish a feedback mechanism where stakeholders can report issues or suggest improvements. This can help identify potential problems early and keep the system updated.
5. **Regular Audits:** Conduct regular audits of the data chain to identify and address any gaps or inefficiencies.
6. **Stakeholder Engagement:** Actively engage all stakeholders in the process to ensure everyone is committed to the success of the TN-ITS data chain. This could involve regular meetings, workshops, or other forms of engagement.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the evaluation process has underscored a critical communication gap within the organization, which has had a significant impact on the effectiveness of the TN-ITS service. The service, designed to streamline and enhance the exchange of speed limit data, has had limited data recording and a lack of interdepartmental communication. This has led to an incomplete and potentially inaccurate GIS database, undermining the reliability of the service. The issue underscores the importance of effective communication and data sharing within an organization. These elements are crucial to ensuring the accuracy and integrity of services like TN-ITS, which rely heavily on up-to-date and accurate data. Without effective communication channels, vital information can be lost or misinterpreted, leading to inaccuracies in the data and, consequently, the services provided.

Looking ahead, it is imperative that future efforts focus on addressing these communication issues. In addition, improving data collection and sharing practices should be a priority. This could involve investing in more advanced data collection tools, implementing more thorough data validation processes, and ensuring that all relevant departments have access to the data they need. By addressing these issues, we can enhance the effectiveness and reliability of the TN-ITS service, ultimately contributing to safer and more efficient road

networks. This will not only benefit road users but also pave the way for advancements in autonomous vehicle technology.

Acknowledgements

This research was funded by the Public Works Department (PWD) of the Ministry of Transport, Communications and Works of Cyprus, under a research contract with the University of Cyprus, through the KIOS Research and Innovation Centre of Excellence (KIOS CoE) for the fiscal years 2022-2026. The work of authors has been partially supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 739551 (KIOS CoE) and by the Republic of Cyprus through the Deputy Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digital Policy as well as the NAPCORE project under the grand agreement No. MOVE/B4/SUB/2020-123/SI2.852232. The authors would like to express their gratitude to all PWD employees for their valuable assistance, during the preparation of this work as well as the contributions from the Police officer George Milis at the Office of Road Safety.

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